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Analysis of east java mata masyarakat hospital based on malcolm baldrige performance criteria

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Abstract

A hospital is a health service institution that provides complete individual health services, providing inpatient, outpatient and emergency services. Quality of Service is one form of effort made by each Hospital in carrying out actions that make patients feel comfortable, safe, fast and precise in getting their needs. This research aims to explain performance analysis using the Malcolm Baldrige criteria in hospitals Mata Masyarakat of East Java. This research is a cross-sectional study where data is collected at a certain time to describe the situation at that time. Employees selected as respondents will fill out a questionnaire that has been prepared with a number of questions based on Malcolm Baldrige's criteria. The data that will be taken in the research is the characteristics of employees at the hospital Mata Masyarakat and performance measurement based on hospital employee perceptions. The population in this study were hospital employees Mata Masyarakat are 40 employees consisting of management staff and unit heads. In this study, the samples used were managers and unit heads in hospitals Mata Masyarakat are 30 people. The research results show that the criteria with the highest percentage scores are Customer Focus, Process Management and Results with each score (85%) while the lowest is Leadership with a score of (79%). total score obtained by hospital Mata Masyarakat's score for all Malcolm Baldrige Criteria based on the questionnaire results is 837.6 or 83.69% of the maximum score of 1000 which is in the very good category.

Keywords: Malcolm Baldrige; Performance; East Java Mata Masyarakat Hospital

1. Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic that has hit Indonesia since March 2020 has caused changes in various aspects of life, especially having a significant impact on the aspect of public health. Thus, the implementation of health sector programs is now focused on handling Covid-19. Covid 19 demands changes, both in terms of ways of thinking, ways of behaving and ways of working. The next challenge is a way of thinking and behaving that can improve the level of public health and be resilient to the threat of disease, including the diseases of tomorrow. The role of public health workers is very important in handling Covid-19 at every level of intervention. Primarily at the community level to carry out risk communication and public education regarding health protocols to fight Covid-19. Then to carry out contact tracing & tracking (case investigation and outbreak investigation), as well as community facilitation and empowerment.

Public health has an important role in efforts to improve the quality of human resources, poverty alleviation and economic development. The Human Development Index places health as one of the main components of measurement besides education and income. The general condition of Indonesia's health is influenced by environmental factors, behavior and health services. Meanwhile, health services consist of several components, including the availability and quality of health service facilities, medicines and health supplies, health personnel, financing and health management. Basic health service facilities, namely Community Health Centers which are strengthened by Assistant Community

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Health Centers and Mobile Community Health Centers, have been established in almost all regions of Indonesia, but the distribution and affordability of health services is still an obstacle (Firman, 2022).

According to the Indonesian Ministry of Health (2019), health facilities are public facilities which refer to facilities or infrastructure or equipment that are realized in the form of services provided by regional governments and the private sector with the aim of maintaining and improving health. Health equipment includes health facilities which are an important factor in providing health services. Health facilities that are said to be good must meet several requirements, including the number and type of equipment according to the company's service needs, be easily recognized and become its own characteristic, have complete distribution permits in accordance with statutory provisions, have quality, security and safety standards, and have been tested and calibrated regularly. periodically by authorized testing and calibrating institutions.

One of the health facilities that supports public health is a hospital. WHO (World Health Organization) states that an integral part of a social and health organization with the function of providing plenary (comprehensive) services, curing disease (curative) and preventing disease (preventive) to the community is a hospital. This shows that the role of hospitals in the regions, whether private or government owned, will help meet the community's needs regarding health services. Meanwhile, when referring to the regulations of UU No. 44/2009 which states that a hospital is a health service institution that provides comprehensive individual health services that provide inpatient, outpatient and emergency services. From this explanation, it can be interpreted that hospitals have different service facilities according to the condition of patients who wish to undergo treatment or consultation regarding health.

Quality of Service is one form of effort made by each Hospital in carrying out actions that make patients feel comfortable, safe, fast and precise in getting their needs. The level of service of a hospital will help create a sense of satisfaction in patients who receive treatment or health consultations from the hospital. Measuring patient satisfaction with a hospital will help create a good image of the hospital. This is very important for hospital management to know in order to evaluate and improve strategies in providing services to the community.

This research was conducted based on information regarding a decrease in public satisfaction at a hospital in Surabaya, namely hospital Mata Masyarakat of East Java. Mata Masyarakat Hospital originally called Mata Masyarakat Health Center was founded on April 18 1992 under the Indonesian Ministry of Health. Based on Minister of Health Decree No. 909 / Menkes / SK /VIII / 2001 dated 4 April 2001 concerning the institutional transfer of several Technical Service Units within the Ministry of Health to become regional apparatus, at that time Mata Masyarakat Health Center's authority was transferred to the Regional Government of East Java Province and was under the Health Service East Java Province. However, after a long time it turned out that there was a problem regarding the decline in the Community Satisfaction Index in 2021.

In 2019 the value of the Community Satisfaction Index was 77.62% then rose to 79.32% in 2020. This has a positive trend which shows that community satisfaction has increased in 2020. However, in the following year the level of satisfaction decreased from 79.32 % to 78.71% in 2021. This is one of the reasons for this research, which is to see what can influence hospital patient satisfaction Mata Masyarakat. In this research, the quality of services and facilities available at the hospital East Java Mata Masyarakat, used to measure Patient Satisfaction. The highest Community Satisfaction Index is the standard for achieving East Java Mata Masyarakat Hospital Community Satisfaction Index, namely 79.32%.

A good level of public satisfaction will be able to describe the existing performance of a hospital agency, whether private or government owned, so that in assessing the existence of good service in a hospital, it is necessary to know the efforts that can be made to improve performance. So this research took the initiative to measure the performance of a hospital using the Malcolm Baldrige criteria. The Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (MBNQA) is a tool that can be used to measure the effectiveness of overall organizational performance, both for companies, educational and health organizations. Malcolm Baldrige's educational criteria for excellent performance is the basis for conducting self-assessments of an organization, in order to get awards and provide feedback to the organization.

2. Material and methods

This research data was obtained from conducting a survey of hospital employees Mata Masyarakat of East Java. Meanwhile, according to time, this research is included in cross-sectional research where data is collected at a certain time to describe the situation at that time. Employees selected as respondents will fill out a questionnaire that has been prepared with a number of questions based on Malcolm Baldrige's criteria. The data that will be taken in the research is the characteristics of employees at the hospital Mata Masyarakat of the East Java and performance measurement

based on hospital employee perceptions. The population in this study were hospital employees Mata Masyarakat of the East Java are 40 employees consisting of management staff and unit heads. In this study, the samples used were managers and unit heads in hospitals Mata Masyarakat of the East Java are 30 people consisting of Management and Unit Heads.

In this research, the researcher used a purposive sampling method, namely a sampling technique that is based on the researcher's considerations regarding which samples are most appropriate, useful and considered to be representative of a population (representative). This sampling technique tends to have higher sample quality. Because researchers have created a grid or boundaries based on certain criteria that will be used as research samples. For example, based on demographic characteristics, gender, type of work, age and so on. This technique is a sampling technique that is quite often used in research.

In this study, the location used was a hospital Mata Masyarakat of the East Javanese whose address is Jl. Ketintang Baru Sel. No.1, Ketintang, Kec. Gayungan, SBY City, East Java. The time used by researchers for this research was carried out from the date the research permit was issued, a period of approximately 2 (two) months.

In this research, the initial process carried out was to identify performance using the Malcolm Baldrige criteria at the East Java Mata Masyarakat Hospital. The Malcolm Baldrige criteria used in this research consist of 7 criteria including Leadership Criteria, Strategic Planning Criteria, Customer Focus Criteria, Measurement, Analysis and Management Knowledge Criteria, Workforce Focus Criteria, Process and Results Management Criteria. After identifying performance using the Malcolm Baldrige criteria, the next step is to carry out an assessment or scoring using predetermined rules. After the score is calculated, the score achieved by the hospital's performance will be known Mata Masyarakat of the East Javanese so that overall performance can be described. After the hospital performance score Mata Masyarakat of East Java are known, then an analysis of the performance achievements of each criterion whose value is known will be carried out. So you can know the criteria that require the greatest quality improvement.

In this study, obtaining data directly was carried out using a questionnaire. In the questionnaire used, the level of respondents' answers was determined using a Likert scale. The questionnaires that have been provided by researchers will later be given to hospital patients Mata Masyarakat of the East Java are in accordance with the specified sample size. Each statement in the questionnaire in this study uses a score of 1-4 with an explanation, namely Strongly Agree (SS) score 4, Agree (S) score 3, Disagree (TS) score 2, and Strongly Disagree (STS) score 1. Next, the criteria for each variable will be known using percentage calculations.

The Percentage Criteria for the Poor Assessment is if the existing value has a percentage between 0-25%, the Fairly Good Criteria is obtained if the percentage is in the range of 26%-50%, while for the Good assessment it is obtained if the percentage range is between 51%-75%, and a Very good value is obtained. It is good if the percentage range is between 76%-100%. Meanwhile, to calculate the total score for the Malcolm Baldrige category, you need to multiply the average percentage obtained by the total score for each Malcolm Baldrige category for which the points have been determined.

3. Results and discussion

In this case, the score achieved in the research will be seen for all assessment criteria based on the results of the questionnaire, this can be seen in the following table :

Table 1 Scores for All Criteria Based on Hospital Questionnaire Results Mata Masyarakat of East Java.

No	Criteria	Maximum Score	Score	Item Score	Criteria Score
1	Leadership	120			94.8
	Senior Leader	70	78.7%	55	
	Governance and Social Responsibility	50	79.7%	39.8	
2	Strategic Planning	85			71
	Strategy Development	40	83.0%	33.2	
	Strategy Implementation	45	84.0%	37,8	

3	Customer Focus	85			72.2
	Customer Engagement	40	81.5%	32.6	
	Customer Complaints	45	88.0%	39.6	
4	Measurement, Analysis, and Knowledge, Management	90			74.6
	Measurement, Analysis and Improvement of Organizational Performance	45	81.7%	36.8	
	Management of Information, Knowledge and Information Technology	45	84.0%	37.8	
5	Workforce Focus	85			68.8
	Workforce Engagement	45	76.5%	34	
	Workforce Environment	40	87.0%	34.8	
6	Process Management	85			72.2
	Work system	35	86.7%	30.3	
	Work process	50	83.7%	41.9	
7	Results	450			384
	Product Results	100	83.0%	83	
	Customer Focused Results	70	90.0%	63	
	Financial and Market Results	70	88.0%	61.6	
	Workforce-Focused Outcomes	70	83.0%	58.1	
	Process Effectiveness Results	70	89.0%	62.3	
	Leadership Results	70	79.0%	55.3	
Total		1000	83,69%		837.6

Table 1 shows the total score obtained by hospital Mata Masyarakat East Java's score for all Malcolm Baldrige Criteria based on the questionnaire results is 837.6 or 83.69% of the maximum score of 1000 which is in the very good category. The criterion with the highest score is results (384), and the lowest is workforce focus (68.8).

After determining the predicate and level of hospital performance Mata Masyarakat of the East Javanese are based on Malcolm Baldrige, then the next step is to analyze the relationship between the criteria in the process dimension and the criteria for results. Analysis was carried out by carrying out the Pearson correlation test on the questionnaire data. The relationship between the process dimension criteria and the results criteria can be seen in the following table.

Table 2 Relationship between Malcolm Baldrige Criteria and Outcome Criteria.

No	Criteria	Significance	Correlation Coefficient
1	Leadership	0.015	0.272
2	Strategic Planning	0.033	0.460
3	Customer Focus	0.045	0.243
4	Measurement. Analysis. and Knowledge. Management	0.035	0.411
5	Workforce Focus	0.011	0.458
6	Process Management	0.025	0.418

The conclusion drawn by referring to the basis for decision making for the correlation test in table 2 is that it shows that the Malcolm Baldrige criteria have a significant (meaningful) relationship with all of the Malcolm Baldrige criteria with a significance value ($p < 0.05$), where all of these criteria have a significance value of less than from 0.05. Meanwhile, for the level of strength (closeness) of the relationship between the results criteria and the Malcolm Baldrige criteria, the strategic planning criteria are criteria that have a close relationship with the results criteria, because they have the highest correlation coefficient value, namely 0.460.

3.1. Leadership

Leadership is a process by which a person can influence his subordinates in implementing and achieving the vision, mission, and tasks, or objectives, thereby bringing the organization more advanced and united. A leader carries out this process by applying his own leadership traits, namely beliefs, values, ethics, character, knowledge and skills (Syahril, 2019). In the Baldrige Excellence Framework, leadership is defined as the guidance and visible participation carried out by senior leaders in creating organizational values, direction, performance expectations and social responsibility.

Results of research on hospital performance the views of the Mata Masyarakat of East Java as measured by the leadership variable in the Baldrige criteria show that the fulfillment of these criteria is very good. It can be seen in table 1 where the leadership variable got a score of 79%, with an achievement score of 94.8 out of 120 points. However, there are several parts that should be improved according to the results of the respondent's questionnaire with the lowest score, namely regarding the delivery of the vision and mission by the leadership during meetings so that every management and head of units in the Hospital continues to remember the goals that must be achieved while working. In an organization, vision and mission are the main keys to carrying out all activities in the organization. Vision and mission are at the top before planning in the organization. The vision provides a clear picture of the future that can be seen by consumers, employees or other stakeholders. A good vision statement is not only inspiring and challenging, but also so meaningful that every employee can connect the tasks they perform with the vision. The vision statement must be able to inspire every action taken by every employee. The most important thing is that the vision statement must be measurable so that every employee can know whether the actions they take are in order to achieve the organization's vision or not. And this vision must be translated directly into the organization's mission statement.

Mission is the main activity that must be carried out or function carried out by an organization to achieve the vision that has been designed. The organization's mission statement must be broad enough to accommodate future organizational developments. The organization's mission must be able to clearly show a picture of what will be achieved in the future. The organization's mission should be easy to understand. A mission that is easy to understand will make it easier to communicate the mission to members of the organization. The organization's mission contains the main reason for the existence of the organization or institution. The philosophy, values and culture of the organization are also reflected in the organization's mission.

Researchers obtained information from sources that the vision, mission and values had been socialized by senior leaders to all internal stakeholders of the hospital, but the explanation was not implemented intensively. Senior leaders need to establish performance measures so that the achievement of the Vision and Mission can be measured, analyzed and improved. From the research results, the size and level of success in achieving the Vision and Mission have not been determined. The medical committee is also not functioning properly, even though this is important to avoid claims from patients and the public for malpractice. In the MBNQA assessment, compliance with laws and ethical behavior is very important to be created and implemented by senior leadership. When compared with the achievements of hospital senior leadership Mata Masyarakat of the East Javanese in the Vision and Mission goal area can be said to still be at an early stage in a systematic approach.

3.2. Strategic Planning

Results of research on hospital performance Mata Masyarakat of the East Javanese as measured through the Strategy planning variable in the Baldrige criteria show that the fulfillment of these criteria is Very Good. It can be seen in table 1 where the Strategy planning variable got a score of 84%, with an achievement score of 71 out of 85 points. However, there are several parts that should be improved according to the results of the respondent's questionnaire with the lowest score, namely regarding the analysis that needs to be carried out in making the right strategy according to the needs of patients in the hospital, then carrying out evaluation results related to the achievements of the strategies that have been made previously. needs to be improved.

This strategy criterion describes the relationship between organizational quality planning and overall organizational planning. In order to achieve excellent performance, quality improvement planning must be fully integrated into the organization's competitive strategy. Strategic quality planning must be able to include the implementation and

development of work plans, complete with priority scale and required resources. Strategic planning emphasizes the importance of organizations in responding to and responding to various environmental changes that are dynamic and difficult to predict. The strategic planning process involves senior management and managers from business units or other key responsibility centers, and is assisted by their respective staff. In the Baldrige Excellence Framework, it is explained that strategy development must be a reference for organizations to prepare for the future. Strategy development is carried out by existing leaders and teams by utilizing various types of estimates, projections, options, scenarios, information that is relevant to the organization.

The Baldrige concept not only relies on developing strategic plans, but also emphasizes the ability of organizations and leaders to disseminate these strategic plans and translate them into key indicators that are easy to understand and implement in daily activities. Dissemination of organizational strategy requires integrated efforts by elements of senior leadership and technical leadership to create communicative media so that all parties in the organization can be involved in efforts to achieve the goals of the established strategy.

Hospital Mata Masyarakat of East Java basically already have work plans, but these plans do not yet synergize with the strategic plans that have been prepared. The work plan is an effort to achieve the hospital's strategic targets. The strategic targets are set and adjusted to the vision and mission they carry. Strategy goals are converted into Work Plans. The Work Plan is explained to all work units. Every year the hospital evaluates the work plan so that the process occurs learning even though it is still in the general improvement stage, it has not shown any innovation. The organization's ability to develop strategies well will provide opportunities for innovation and as a performance reference that can understand the organization's core competencies, be able to compete and collaborate with various parties now and in the future. Good strategic planning will be a change that may affect the performance of organizational services, increase innovation and the ability to take advantage of a variety of opportunities, and can direct resources to better prioritize in dealing with health, social, ethical, regulatory, technological, service issues. security, and other potential risks including to prevent and respond to emergencies, and other natural disasters, as well as changes in the national and global economy.

3.3. Customer Focus

Results of research on hospital performance Mata Masyarakat of East Java as measured through the Customer Focus variable in the Baldrige criteria show that the fulfillment of this criterion is very good. It can be seen in table 1 where the customer focus variable gets a score of 85%, with an achievement score of 72.2 out of 85 points. However, there are several areas that should be improved according to the results of the respondent's questionnaire with the lowest score, namely regarding the existence of a mechanism that is able to provide results not only in service efforts but also in seeing loyal patients, including the sense of satisfaction that they convey from their attitude and way of communicating.

Referring to the research results, to find out which patients are loyal to the hospital Mata Masyarakat of the East Java, carried out using an approach through internal hospital reports, grouping customers based on geography and characteristics. With this segmentation, loyal hospital customers can be identified. Having clear segmentation will help an organization to provide a service that suits customer needs.

The customer focus approach is still very lacking because it is only based on customer data, there is no approach to outpatients. In inpatient care, the methods used are also limited to the nursing field. Based on the results of interviews and documents, it is known that data relating to service performance is reported routinely every month in the medical records section, but is never analyzed to determine market segmentation. It should be to know its customers, hospital Mata Masyarakat of the East Java can approach this through internal hospital reports from the medical records department every month, and then segment customers demographically. Apart from that, there needs to be an evaluation in the mechanism so that every patient who comes does not complain about the long time it takes to get service.

3.4. Measurement, Analysis, and Knowledge, Management

Results of research on hospital performance Mata Masyarakat of the East Javanese as measured through measurement, analysis and management knowledge variables in the Baldrige criteria show that the fulfillment of these criteria is Very Good. It can be seen in table 1 where the measurement, analysis and management knowledge variables got a score of 83%, with an achievement score of 74.6 out of 90 points. However, there are several areas that should be improved according to the results of the respondent's questionnaire with the lowest score, namely regarding responses that are still not fast enough in emergency conditions in hospitals so this needs to be improved in an effort to provide maximum service to the community and then there is also a need for analysis of an existing problem so that the actions that can be taken are measurable and do not stray from the focus of solving the problem.

Data analysis is important for an organization to make decisions. This is intended to avoid facts and data that are not related to priority setting and effective decision making. Referring to the research results, it is known that hospital Mata Masyarakat of East Java have not yet carried out comprehensive data analysis. Performance reviews are carried out only when problems arise, not routinely or periodically to monitor existing developments. Through systematic data collection and an effective analysis support system, it will become the basis for reliable decision making. Harmony between analysis and organizational performance review must be realized, as well as between analysis and organizational planning. This ensures that decision making is in line with analysis based on appropriate data and information.

The measurement results of this variable describe the respondent's perception that hospital Mata Masyarakat of East Java are currently still not good at measuring and analyzing performance for the purpose of improving performance. Hospital staff are still considered unable to measure the implementation of the work they have done, such as the lack of good response to patients who come. Based on the instruments owned by the hospital and the work plans that have been made by each work unit, each employee should be able to carry out independent measurements of their work results, but not all employees can do this well.

3.5. Workforce Focus

Results of research on hospital performance Mata Masyarakat of the East Javanese as measured by the workforce focus variable in the Baldrige criteria show that the fulfillment of these criteria is very good. It can be seen in table 1 where the workforce focus variable got a score of 81%, with an achievement score of 68.8 out of 85 points. However, there are several areas that should be improved according to the results of the respondent's questionnaire with the lowest score, namely regarding employee placement which is still not appropriate according to the results of the questionnaire. This will prevent the hospital from providing maximum service to existing patients. This is due to limited human resources in hospitals.

Good work results are due to the existence of human resources who are able to work according to their potential. Therefore, management and placement of employees is one of the factors that will help the hospital achieve its stated goals. In the existing conditions, it turns out that there is a shortage of skilled workers and a work system that is still beyond the capabilities of employees, which is the cause of a deficiency in placing employees according to their potential, so it is necessary to have a system that regulates work effectiveness and a financial system as a form of developing the potential of human resources. in the hospital, whether in relation to recruitment or carrying out job training and also developing existing facilities in the hospital.

3.6. Process Management

Results of research on hospital performance Mata Masyarakat of the East Javanese as measured by the work process management variable in the Baldrige criteria show that the fulfillment of these criteria is very good. It can be seen in table 1 where the process management variable gets a score of 85%, with an achievement score of 72.2 out of 85 points. However, there are several parts that should be improved according to the results of the respondent's questionnaire with the lowest scores, namely regarding Risk Management, Evacuation and Recovery which are carried out only when there is a need or are still not implemented within a certain routine period and the processes in the service mechanism are carried out to achieve Management performance and The Unit Head has not been able to create a sense of satisfaction with the services provided to customers.

Based on the research results, it shows that there are documents, the process of determining the main services at the hospital Mata Masyarakat of the East Javanese have not gone through an identification process based on needs planning which is then analyzed, and have not accommodated input from internal and external customers. A cost and benefit analysis has also not been carried out, as a way to ensure the decision to open the service is the right one.

3.7. Results

The results in Table 1 above show that the questionnaire score for the results criteria which consists of 6 statements is 384 or 85% of the maximum score for this criterion (450). The statement in this Criteria that has the highest percentage is that the hospital has improved its services to achieve patient satisfaction with a percentage of 90%, then the statement with the lowest percentage is regarding Coordination between leadership and Management and the Unit Head which has been carried out well which is able to produce good team performance. more optimal in providing services to patients with a percentage of 79%. This is very important to pay attention to because communication in an organization is the beginning of the process that someone will carry out, so there needs to be action and supervision of every line in the hospital Mata Masyarakat of the East Java are to work according to existing SOPs and directions.

4. Conclusion

The research results show that the criteria with the highest percentage scores are Customer Focus, Process Management and Results with each score (85%) while the lowest is Leadership with a score of (79%). total score obtained by hospital Mata Masyarakat's score for all Malcolm Baldrige Criteria based on the questionnaire results is 837.6 or 83.69% of the maximum score of 1000 which is in the very good category.

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